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An Eye Color Recognition App Based on a Convolutional Neural Network

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Introduction

In the basic study of eye and eye color detection, the eyes are the most prominent features of the human compared to the nose and mouth. Eye color detection is a sub-field or sub-category of object detection in image processing and has been widely applied in many fields e.g. in drowsiness detection for an intelligent system, ethnic classification, automatic face detection, and recognition system, and also in human-robot interaction. The complexity in eye detection is mostly due to the structural individualities of the eyes, which vary across different races of the world, and for ethnicity classification, this individuality is very useful. This structural individuality includes the iris color, the size of the eye, and the boldness of the eyelid, additional factors such as contact lens, change in illu-

Abstract: *Eye color detection in image recognition plays an important role in several fields not only because the eyes provide important information about facial feature extraction, but it also provides the concepts behind ethnic recognition in various regions. The paper investigates a semi-hybrid model for eye color detection, it designs an application integrated with a classifier such as a Convolutional Neural Network to improve the speed in detection and eye variance filter. Its accuracy classifies normal features from abnormal features and colors and demonstrates the robustness of the method on three different epochs on facial images.*

Keywords: *Eye color variation, convolutional neural networks, Coding phase, Eye detection, Feature extraction, Probability distribution*

mination, and facial profile introduce noise to the eye and eye color detection and this could lead to a false alarm. This paper discusses eye color authentication

for an individual by using CNN as an inference engine to classify and predict

the eye color of a person that relays

a person's personal information

from a demography database,

a soft biometric trait is designed that provides a novel

insight about the details of

the person of relevant factors

or characteristics in its context.

Apart from eye color authentication,

other factors such as system

information are also provided.

One of the major contributions of the

paper is the fact that since

eye color is one of the essential

features in facial recognition

for every person, it is employed

here for lopping the search

system (the soft biometric) for

individual re-authentication. The

eye color is detected based on

frontal static images and a coding

phase is employed to enhance the

processing speed. Related detected

results and performance for the

CNN model are discussed in the

result section.

Figure 1: Database of the front profile of people with different eye color from an online and local group.

Literature Review

Research has found that soft biometric traits use weak biometric descriptive characteristics that are often common among individuals and are often termed as not important and non-permanent and help to differentiate individuals in facial recognition (Reid et al. [1, 2], Nixon et al. [3, 4], Bekhouche [5]). Most of these characteristics have a certain advantage that acquires a lack of consent from the individuals being surveyed. The evaluation of the soft biometric can be free of mishaps because class training is performed in advance on the subjects based on a specific authentication (Dantcheva et al. [6], Kumar et al. [7], Jan et al. [8], DeAndres-Tame et al. [9], Sargas and Ball [10]). In the current research, these traits have been identified as possible descriptive features for a person, these traits such as eye color, gender, and hair color (Vaquero et al. [11], Dantcheva et al. [12], Walsh et al. [13], WURMBACH [14]) have brought about the need to efficiently categorise the set of input matrix in this paper we briefly focus on optimisation by running CNN of different epochs.

A new area of research that constitutes eye color detection in its full content, focuses on eye color information and corresponding demography data that constitutes the best match (Valenzuela et al. [15], Dandona et al. [16], Sulem et al. [17], Verma et al. [18], Frichot et al. [19], Marmor et al. [20]). The eye color information has been disregarded by traditional iris pattern and texture recognition. Most human eye color region consists of a plethora of biometric traits which has different importance such as the iris and retina patterns with eyebrow size and shape, mapped with the eye color. In most studies, eyes have been subtly neglected simply because 92% of the subjects possess brown eyes (Dantcheva et al. [21], Emery [22], Dantcheva et al. [23], Posner et al.

[24], Cumming [25], Ramos et al. [26]). For Caucasian, the eye color characteristic is of a higher variation than the other ethnic regions. Eye color is mostly determined by the number of pigments in the eyes and is generally an inherited gene, this is the most important attribute for a soft biometric trait.

Studies (Flament et al. [27], Barbur and Rodriguez-Carmona [28], Paramei [29], Roy et al. [30]) have shown that eye color changes with time and in 30-40 years. The extraction of eye color is a very realistic process and the cascaded detected area could be around 12mm, where the color on its own is deduced by illumination and sensitivity. Another issue that arises in eye color detection is variability in size e.g. in pupil size due to natural illumination. The positive factors involve the feasibility of eye color which can accurately be detected by low-cost surveillance sensors and are available, these can provide high resolution.

Though there is preliminary scientific research (Remeseiro et al. [31], Wrolstad and Smith [32], Burlina et al. [33]) on eye color detection it is mostly based on subjective human color grading and human analysis of eye color texture and initial detection attempts. This paper differentiates its method by applying CNN at different epochs for color classification from a static image which also users' demography as additional user characteristics. The method is discussed in the proceeding section.

Method

The method adopted for the proposed coding phase is based on an explicit specification of input layers (an encoded version of the input capture from the lens of a mobile phone) this is represented as a static motion mode design for the feed-in inference engine (CNN). The initial state is creating and training a new CNN by defining its network architecture for image sequence classification and SoftMax (Figure 2). This architecture can vary depending on the different types and counts of layers represented by the input model and a particular application or data model. For this version, Matlab was used as the tool for data analysis. The analytical tool was designed using GUI libraries that created a custom network architecture, classification, and SoftMax model layers as the back-end (Figure 2). The eye image capture for color detection is saved in sequential order and a typical coding phase was used for optimisation (Figure 3 Algorithm 1). This utilises an averagely complex data matrix like the one obtained from the dynamic image capture of the eyes and pigments.

Figure 2: Convolutional neural network model for eye classification using Softmax activation on three different epochs for five classes of eye color.

$$\text{Layer} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 \text{imageInputLayer}([28, 28, 1]) \\
 \text{Convolution2dLayer}(3, 26, 2' \text{Padd}') \\
 \text{batchNormalisationLayer} \\
 \text{reluLayer} \\
 \text{MaxPooling2dLayer}(2, \text{Stride}', 2) \\
 \text{Convolution2dLayer}(4, 32, \text{Padd}') \\
 \text{batchNormalisationLayer} \\
 \text{reluLayer} \\
 \text{fullyconnectLayer}(12) \\
 \text{SoftmaLayer} \\
 \text{ClassificationLayer};
 \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

The layer involves an array of layered objects that are used as input to the train function. For specification purposes, we created a network architecture with the entire layer connected sequentially as used in standard procedure, where an array of layers has multiple inputs to produce multiple outputs like the classes of the eye to be detected. This is grouped in *Blue*, *Black*, *Brown*, *Green* and *Hazel*. The novel approach here is creating layer classification for the eye color as a 2D convolution layer module (Figure 2) with a sliding convolutional filter to the 2D input:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x, & x \geq 0 \\ 0, & x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where x is the input matrix or value less than zero for the normalisation state of each element x in the input i.e. the trained network computes the value X_n , such that:

$$X_n = \frac{x}{K + \left(\frac{\delta(S_s)}{\text{windowSize}}\right)^\alpha} \quad (3)$$

Where K , δ and α are the hyperplane parameter in the normalisation, S_s is the sum of all squares of each element

in a given window frame i.e. before the static resultant output image is detected for the mapped pupil color. The Mean Square Error (MSE) result for the output is given as:

$$MSE = \sum_{(i=1)}^R \frac{(t_i - y_i)^2}{R} \quad (4)$$

Where R is the number of an output response, t_i the target output and y_i the network prediction for the next pupil change response i to color i , this is used to obtain the Tracker operating characteristics for a hundred percent score as discussed in the result section.

Result

The criteria of reliability in designing an automatic eye color detection model have to be met before the choice of method of procedure for the iris extraction and color classification, though manual iris extraction is not applicable in this case. The time and computational efficiency have to be maintained. This result section presents a classification method and examination of different color of facial profiles in a large database captured for iris color detection. A total of 100 profiles were first captured, and based on the phasing coding scheme several profiles were matched to their exact color. Each profile contains freeware images of people online and locally captured images offline. Each profile was grouped in an unsupervised manner and the inference engine (CNN) was allowed to group the data and extract the best and exact possible match, each subject features diverse illuminations and iris positions. The soft biometric method presented also can detect the cognitive state of the user at that static point in time. These cognitive states are classified based on dilation for '*intense surprise*' and constriction for '*intense focus*', and we automated the annotation of each

```

function eyeColor(hObject, eventdata, handles)
global rgbEyeColor
EyeDetect = vision.CascadeObjectDetector('EyePairBig');
BB=step(EyeDetect,rgbEyeColor);
rectangle('Position',BB,'LineWidth',4,'LineStyle','-', 'EdgeColor','b');
title('Eyes Detection');
Eyes=imcrop(rgbEyeColor,BB);

black=black_eyes(Eyes1);
blue=blue_eyes(Eyes1);
brown=brown_eyes(Eyes1);
green=green_eyes(Eyes1);
hazel=hazel_eyes(Eyes1);

if sum(sum(black)) > sum(sum(blue)) && sum(sum(black)) > sum(sum(brown)) &&
sum(sum(black)) > sum(sum(green)) && sum(sum(black)) > sum(sum(hazel))
s=(' Black ')

elseif sum(sum(blue)) > sum(sum(black)) && sum(sum(blue)) > sum(sum(brown))
&& sum(sum(blue)) > sum(sum(green)) && sum(sum(blue)) > sum(sum(hazel))
s=(' Blue ')

elseif sum(sum(brown)) > sum(sum(black)) && sum(sum(brown)) > sum(sum(blue))
&& sum(sum(brown)) > sum(sum(green)) && sum(sum(brown)) > sum(sum(hazel))
s=(' Brown ')

elseif sum(sum(green)) > sum(sum(black)) && sum(sum(green)) > sum(sum(blue))
&& sum(sum(green)) > sum(sum(brown)) && sum(sum(green)) > sum(sum(hazel))
s=(' Green ')
else
s=(' Hazel ')
end

```

Figure 3: Algorithm 1: Coding phase for eye color classification using Matlab.

subset of the database and obtained the following five different eye color sets for both the training and test set (Black, Brown, Blue, Green, and Hazel). Figure 4 below, shows an example of an iris detection and color match, the cascaded image detection initially captures the region of the pupil and matches the exact color to its set using Algorithm 1. The match colors were specified and are straight and based on human distinguishing

Figure 4: Iris and eye color detection in synchronous with the cognitive state of the person at the static stage.

The biometric also can record the timestamp and pupil changes which were captured in real-time before a

static position is set for iris detection. The authentication can easily match a pupil's color and personality with the demography of an individual. Figure 5 shows a captured record of an individual with black eye color and ID pass that would be useful for security purposes.

Each set of data for both training and testing uses three different epochs for the CNN, anomalies (outliers) due to noise could be useful for user and behaviour analysis but for the case, these outliers were removed since color classification is directly involved. Figure 6 shows the three different variations in pattern search used three different epochs, these epochs were set based on the rate of speed in detection and search for the best possible accuracy to a match. The epochs are set randomly from 1 to 10 and the variations are not far apart.

The performance for each CNN model is tested to determine the performance rate and tracking operation characteristics for all attributes applied. Figure 7 shows the best possible outcome using a singular epoch at 0.98%. The performance rate can be seen to be close to 100 for each tracking process and shows that a generalised method or process can be adopted regarding a pattern search with CNN.

Conclusion

This paper set out to investigate the possibility of optimising a process using the coding phase for eye color

Basic Information

	2	3
1	Timestamp	Pupil_chan...
2	0	0
3	1	3.5500
4	3	3
5	9	3.2000
6	10	0
7	10	4.1000

BASIC INFO@
 Authentication: Pass
 Authentication ID: 10232
 Eye Color: Black
 Pass Code: 10232

Eye Metrics

Connect to Camera
 Print Receipt
 Download Pass

Re-Authenticate

Figure 5: Captured window form for match result for eye color and user authentication with physiological record readings.

Figure 6: Data variation in Eye color authentication with outliers and three sets of epochs.

recognition with a convolutional neural network. A set of images with different postures in the front profile was obtained online and locally. These images represent a database of color variations from the region of the eyes

Figure 7: Receiver Operating Characteristics for iris detection and tracking.

which is used to produce the best fit for an input image. A coding phase was set to match the color of the eyes to its best possible fit and performance was computed for each input image. The tracking operation characteristics indicate that it is possible to generalize the CNN model without the need for epochs since the rate of performance for each epoch chosen is close to 100%. The future perspective would be to develop parallel processing of images which would be detected in sequential others and an input image would be selected from the parallel classification.

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